

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SELF-MICROEMULSIFYING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM FOR HYPERTENSION

¹Hitesh Chaturvedi, ²Dr. Aniruddh Singh Deora

¹Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacy, Bhupal Nobles' University, Udaipur (Raj.)

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy, Bhupal Nobles' University, Udaipur (Raj.)

Received: Nov 20, 2025

Accepted: Dec 12, 2025

Published: Dec 13, 2025

ABSTRACT

Hypertension or high blood pressure (HBP) is a globally acknowledged warning cry for attention towards one's most important facets of survival, i.e., the functioning of the cardiovascular system. The major component of the cardiovascular system is the heart which energizes the circulatory system in a living being by transporting oxygen, nutrients and other essential gases to body cells through blood circulation. The purpose of this study is to formulate and evaluate a self-micro emulsifying drug delivery system (SMEDDS) to improve the oral absorption of poorly water-soluble Nifedipine. Through the solubility test of Nifedipine in various oils, surfactants and co-surfactants, pharmaceutical excipients were selected.

Keywords: Hypertension, SMEDDS, solubility test

1. INTRODUCTION

Hypertension or high blood pressure (HBP) is a globally acknowledged warning cry for attention towards one's most important facets of survival, i.e., the functioning of the cardiovascular system. The major component of the cardiovascular system is the heart which energizes the circulatory system in a living being by transporting oxygen, nutrients and other essential gases to body cells through blood circulation.^{1,2} This circulation is facilitated through a force of the blood against the blood vessels across the body. Normally, the force of running blood within the circulatory system, referred to as the 'blood pressure'. A long-sustained norm of blood pressure recording is considered within the biological reference range of 120/80 mm/Hg. This reference point is indicative of the

ideal amount of force exerted by the heart to pump the blood to various body parts.^{3,4} The upper number denoted as systolic pressure denotes the active state of the heart, and the lower number denoted as diastolic pressure denotes the pressure of the blood during the resting state of the heart. When this normative range shoots up above 140/90 mm/Hg—a state of hypertension or high blood pressure develops, and if it is consistently above limits, can signal the collapse of the cardiovascular process.^{5,6} However, the latest guidelines provided by the American Heart Association suggest a lower bookmark to diagnose HBP, i.e., 130/85 mm/Hg compared to the sustained norm by the European benchmark of 140/90 mm/Hg to account for the possible complications at lower BP recordings and make space for earlier interventions. It is highly recommended that India adopts the lower criteria for diagnosis in order to counterfeit the alarming low level of BP control which was found to less than 15%. There are no distinct symptoms that alarm this failure, justifying the colloquial usage of the term for HBP – ‘the silent killer’. A diagnosis of hypertension is determined by elevated blood pressure readings of three resting recordings in a span of two clinical visits. A persistent high blood pressure is quantified through monthly monitoring of blood pressure for at least three times using a sphygmomanometer for a minimum of three months according to a criterion provided by the National Institute of Clinical Excellence.^{7,8}

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Analytical method of Nifedipine

2.1.1 Preparation of Standard Solutions of Nifedipine in Buffers

Preparation of standard solution of Nifedipine in Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) 100 mg of Nifedipine was placed in a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in small amount of methanol. The volume was made up to 100 ml with phosphate buffer (pH6.8) to give 1000 µg/ml solution. 1 ml aliquot was taken and diluted to 100 ml with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) to get 10µg/ml. Stock solution (10µg/ml) of Nifedipine was taken to determine the absorption maxima of the drug in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and 0.1N HCl. The solution was scanned on a double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer to determine the absorption maxima of the drug. The drug shows absorption maxima at 240nm.

2.1.2 Preparation of Standard Graphs of Nifedipine in 0.1N HCl

Preparation of standard graph in 0.1N HCl & pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. 100mg of pure Nifedipine was accurately weighed & dissolved in small amount of methanol and diluted to 100 ml with buffer / 0.1N HCl. 10 ml of stock solution-I was transfer into 100ml flask and volume was made up to 1000ml with buffer/0.1N HCl 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2,2.5 and 3 ml was pipetted out & diluted to 10ml to obtain 5,10,15,20, 25 and 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration solutions. The absorbance was measured at 240nm using UV double beam spectrophotometer against respective media blank.

2.1.3 Preparation of standard graph in Methanol

100 mg of Nifedipine was placed in a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in small amount of methanol. The volume was made up to 100 ml with methanol to give 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution. 1 ml aliquot was taken and diluted to 100 ml with methanol to get 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. From this 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5 and 3 ml was pipetted out & diluted to 10 ml to obtain 5,10,15,20, 25 and 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration solutions. The absorbance was measured at 261nm using UV double beam spectrophotometer against the respective media blank.

2.2 Interference Study of Nifedipine with Excipients

In order to ascertain the non-interference of the excipients in estimation of Nifedipine, solutions containing known concentration of each excipient were prepared in methanol and PBS 6.8 containing 1% Tween 80. The prepared solutions were scanned in the UV region between 200-400 nm using the respective blank. Also, to study the effect in presence of drug, Nifedipine solutions (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in methanol as well as in PBS 6.8 containing 1% Tween 80 was spiked with known concentrations of each excipient and scanned in the UV region between 200 nm-400 nm.

2.3 Identification and Characterization by FTIR absorption spectroscopy

The IR Spectrum of the drug samples were recorded using FTIR– Brucker alpha-E model.

2.4 Identification and Characterization by UV absorption spectroscopy

Accurately weighed 25 mg Nifedipine was transferred to 25 ml volumetric flask. Small quantity of methanol was added to ensure complete dissolution of Nifedipine and finally volume was made up to the mark with methanol (1 mg/ml solution). From the above solution, 5ml of solution was withdrawn accurately with the help of pipette and transferred to 50ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with methanol to make stock solution (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). 1 ml of this solution

was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted with methanol to make up the volume. Then the prepared solution of Nifedipine (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was scanned using Shimadzu double beam UV-visible spectrophotometer from wavelength 200-400 nm range using methanol as blank. Absorption maximum (λ_{max}) was obtained at 360 nm

3. RESULTS

3.1 Analytical Method Development of Nifedipine

Determination of Nifedipine λ_{max} in Methanol. Dilutions of Nifedipine were made in methanol and scanned in UV region using UV Visible double beam spectrophotometer. Absorption maxima of Nifedipine in methanol was found to be 240nm.

Figure 1. UV spectrum of Nifedipine in Methanol

3.2 Preparation of standard graph of Nifedipine in Methanol

Standard dilutions of Nifedipine in the range of 5 to 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were prepared and absorbances were taken against methanol as blank. The standard curve of Nifedipine was plotted from this data.

Figure 2. Standard graph of Nifedipine in Methanol

The standard graph of Nifedipine is shown in Figure. It is linear in the range of 5 to 30 µg/ml. The linear regression equation is $y=0.0233x+0.0014$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of the regression line is 0.999.

3.3 Determination of Nifedipine λ_{\max} in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Dilutions of Nifedipine were made in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and scanned in UV region using UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer. Absorption maxima of Nifedipine in phosphate buffer was found to be 350nm.

Figure 3. UV spectrum of Nifedipine in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

3.4 Preparation of standard graph of Nifedipine in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Standard dilutions of Nifedipine in the range of 5 to 30 µg/ml were prepared and absorbances were taken against buffer as blank. The standard curve of Nifedipine was plotted from this data.

Absorbance values of Nifedipine were recorded at different concentrations in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Figure 4. Standard graph of Nifedipine in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

The standard graph of Nifedipine is shown in Figure. It is linear in the range of 5 to 30 µg/ml. The linear regression equation is $y=0.0226x+0.0074$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of the regression line is 0.9988.

3.5 Determination of absorption maxima of Nifedipine in 0.1N HCl

Dilutions of Nifedipine were made in pH 0.1N HCl and scanned in UV region using UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer. Absorption maxima of Nifedipine in 0.1N HCl was found to be 261nm.

Figure 5. UV spectrum of Nifedipine in pH 0.1N HCl

3.6 Preparation of standard graph of Nifedipine in 0.1N HCl

Standard dilutions of Nifedipine in the range of 5 to 30 µg/ml were prepared and absorbances were taken at 261nm. Standard curve of Nifedipine was plotted from this data.

Figure 6. Standard Graph of Nifedipine in 0.1N HCl

The standard graph of Nifedipine is shown in figure it is linear in the range of 5 to 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The linear regression equation is $y=0.0223x+0.0086$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of the regression line is 0.9992.

3.7 Interference Study of Nifedipine with Excipients

Figure 7. UV Spectrum of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Nifedipine solution in absence and presence of excipients in PBS pH 6.8 containing 1% Tween 80

3.8 Identification and Characterization by FTIR absorption spectroscopy

Figure 8. FTIR Spectra of sample Nifedipine

3.9 Identification and Characterization by UV absorption spectroscopy

Figure 9. UV spectra of sample Nifedipine in Methanol

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Analytical method development for Nifedipine involved UV–Vis spectrophotometric evaluation in different media and characterization by FTIR. The λ_{max} of Nifedipine was determined as 240 nm in methanol, 350 nm in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, and 261 nm in 0.1N HCl. Standard calibration curves prepared over 5–30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in all three media showed excellent linearity, with regression equations $y=0.0233x+0.0014$ ($R^2=0.999$) in methanol, $y=0.0226x+0.0074$ ($R^2=0.9988$) in buffer,

and $y=0.0223x+0.0086$ ($R^2=0.9992$) in HCl. Interference studies confirmed no significant absorbance changes in the presence of excipients. FTIR spectra verified characteristic Nifedipine functional groups, while UV spectra confirmed identity and purity of the sample.

5. REFERENCES

1. Talegaonkar, S., et al., Microemulsions: a novel approach to enhanced drug delivery. *Recent Patents on Drug Delivery Formulation*, 2008. 2(3): p. 238-257.
2. Narang, A.S., D. Delmarre, and D. Gao, Stable drug encapsulation in micelles and microemulsions. *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 2007. 345(1-2): p. 9-25.
3. Kawakami, K., et al., Microemulsion formulation for enhanced absorption of poorly soluble drugs: I. Prescription design. *Journal of controlled release*, 2002. 81(1): p. 65-74.
4. Pouton, C.W., Lipid formulations for oral administration of drugs: nonemulsifying, self-emulsifying and self-microemulsifying drug delivery systems. *European journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 2000. 11: p. S93-S98.
5. Gedil, F., et al., Quantitative determination of felodipine in pharmaceuticals by high pressure liquid chromatography and uv spectroscopy. *Turkish J. Pharm. Sci*, 2004. 1(2): p. 65-76.
6. Yin, Y.M., et al., Docetaxel microemulsion for enhanced oral bioavailability: Preparation and in vitro and in vivo evaluation. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 2009. 140(2): p. 86-94.
7. Gupta, K., A. Wadodkar, and S. Wadodkar, UV-Spectrophotometric methods for estimation of Valsartan in bulk and tablet dosage form. *Inter J ChemTech Res*, 2010. 2(2): p. 985-989.
8. Hauss, D.J., Oral lipid-based formulations. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*, 2007. 59(7): p. 667-676.